

POLYPHEM
THE FUTURE OF SMALL-SCALE CSP PLANTS

POLYPHEM

Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle

D2.6 Enclosure for the Gas Turbine

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Authors Andreas Pöppinghaus, Simon Schütrumpf,
Daniel Ipse

Company KAEFER Isoliertechnik

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Author(s)	Andreas Pöppinghaus, Simon Schütrumpf, Daniel Ipse
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Background: about the POLYPHEM project

FULL TITLE	SMALL-SCALE SOLAR THERMAL COMBINED-CYCLE
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The POLYPHEM project is a research and innovation action funded by the European Union's H2020 program. It is implemented by a European consortium of 4 research centres and 5 industrial partners. The aim is to increase the flexibility and improve the performance of small solar tower power plants. The concept of POLYPHEM consists in implementing a combined cycle formed by a solarized micro gas-turbine and a Rankine organic cycle machine, with an integrated thermal storage device between the two cycles. The need for cooling is minimal.

Developed from a patented technology by CNRS and CEA, the pressurized air solar receiver is integrated in the micro-turbine cycle. The thermal efficiency targeted for the receiver is 80% with a cost of 400 €/kW. The innovative thermal storage uses a thermal oil and a single thermocline tank with a technical concrete filler material.

The main expected impact of this project is to enhance the competitiveness of low-carbon energy production systems through the technology developed. The expected progress is a better fitting of electricity generation to variable local needs, an overall conversion efficiency of solar energy into electricity of 18% for an investment cost of less than 5 €/W and a low environmental impact. By 2030, the cost of electricity production targeted by the POLYPHEM technology is 165 €/MWh for an annual direct normal irradiation of 2600 kWh/m²/year (North Africa and Middle East) and 209 €/MWh under 2050 kWh/m²/year (Southern Europe). In addition to decentralized power generation, other applications are considered for the deployment of this technology used in poly-generation: industrial heat production, solar heating and cooling, desalination of seawater or brackish water.

A prototype plant of 40 kW_{el} with a thermal storage of 1300 kWh is designed, built and installed on the site of the experimental solar tower of Themis in Targassonne (France). The objective of the project is to validate the technical choices under test conditions representative of actual operating conditions.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/abbreviation	Meaning/full text
AALB	Aalborg CSP
ARRA	Arraela S.L.
CA	Consortium Agreement
CEA	Commissariat à l’Energie Atomique
CIEMAT	Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnologicas
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CO	Confidential
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
EURO	Euronovia
FISE	Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems, ISE
M	Month
MS	Milestone
ORC	Orcan Energy GmbH or Organic Rankine Cycle
PU	Public
WP	Work Package

1. DEVELOPMENT OF AN ENCLOSURE FOR THE GAS TURBINE

The enclosure is part of the safety concept. Its purpose is to protect the environment against noise emissions, to serve as a safety cage in case of malfunction and to give shelter for the gas turbine hardware, for a functional liner for cooling air and for the fire extinguishing system.

Figure 1 shows the design of the POLYPHEM gas turbine enclosure. The frame of the enclosure is designed with metal profiles (30 mm x 30 mm x 3 mm). The inner part of the enclosure shall be equipped with stainless steel metal sheets (thickness 3 mm) to provide mechanical protection in case of malfunction. The outer part shall be equipped with aluminium sheets (thickness 1.5 mm).

The ambient air consumed by the turbine (about 1 kg/s) is sucked by the compressor through a large ventilation opening and provides cooling for the generator, the gearboxes, and the pumps of the lubrication oil system. In case of an oil leakage, an oil pan on the bottom of the enclosure shall protect the environment against oil contamination.

For the hot parts of the machine (turbine and exhaust section) a separate chamber within the enclosure was designed to ensure forced cooling of these modules.

The above-mentioned parts have been ordered from a supplier, but the order has been cancelled after it was agreed that the gas turbine will not be operated in Thémis. Indeed, since the testing in solar mode cannot be carried out in the absence of solar receiver and after successful completion of turbine test at KAEPER in Bremen, it was not relevant to install the gas-turbine on site.

Figure 1: Design of POLYPHEM Gas Turbine enclosure

2. FIRE EXTINGUISHING SYSTEM

This system has been designed considering the volume of the enclosure and the air mass flow of the turbine.

It consists of following components:

- CO₂ steel bottle, content: 30 kg CO₂ at 250 bar
- Separate control unit with battery uninterruptible power supply
- Heat detector
- Optical smoke detector
- CO₂ nozzle for hand control
- CO₂ nozzle controlled by control unit
- Horn/ flashlight
- Fire shutter

Figure 2 and Figure 3 show the set-up of the system in the machine room and the components of the system.

Figure 2: Set-up of Fire Extinguishing System in machine room

Figure 3: Components of Fire Extinguishing System and Legend